

Modern Indian English Drama: A Historicist Reading of the Selected Plays

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Abstract— New Historicists are interested in recovering lost histories and in exploring mechanisms of repression and subjugation. The major point to focus is that the New Historicists tend to concentrate on those at the top of the social hierarchy (i.e. the church, the monarchy, the upper-classes) which is a kind of history. New Historicists tend to draw on the disciplines of political science and anthropology given their interest in governments, institutions, and culture. However, New Historicists take this position further by then claiming that all cultural activities may be considered as equally important texts for historical analysis: contemporary trials of hermaphrodites or the intricacies of map-making may inform a Shakespeare play as much as, say, Shakespeare's literary precursors. New Historicism is also more specifically concerned with questions of power and culture. In this paper we focus our new historicist approach on the five selected plays, viz, Larins Saheb by Gurucharan Das, The Refugee Asif Currimbhoy, Lights Out, Manjula Padmanabhan, Worm Play Zubin Driver, Dance like a Man by Mahesh Dattani.

Keywords— Repression, Subjugation, Hermaphrodites, Indian English drama, Historicism

I. INTRODUCTION

The foremost practitioners of New Historicism are Stephen Greenblatt around 1980 and J.W. Lever. Jonathan Dollimore. They defined the term as “The historicity of the text and the textuality of history.”¹ Post Independent era of our country has brought a remarkable change in Indian English Drama. We can see dramas translated from almost all Indian languages. Here, at this juncture the critics really identified the importance of linking history to the literature and widened the scope of literature. According to Jay Stevenson, "New Historicism focuses on the way literature expresses-and sometimes disguises-power relations at work in the social context in which the literature was produced, often this involves making connections between a literary work and other kinds of texts. Literature is often shown to “negotiate” conflicting power interests. New historicism has made its biggest mark on literary studies of the Renaissances and Romantic periods and has revised motions of literature as privileged, apolitical writing. Much new historicism focuses on the marginalization of subjects such as those identified as witches, the insane, heretics, vagabonds, and political prisoners.”²

The new historicists claim that since they see the texts as another artefact of the ideology of a given age, they can go directly to the instruments that constructed the text unmasking their hegemony. And in claiming this, new historicists appropriate two assumptions of post-structuralism: firstly, that a text can only be understood if we lay claims to the ideology of the age and not the intention of the writer; and secondly, the doctrine of textuality (that a literary work is another historical document or a text rooted in the context) is the only means to understand the contextual meaning. Both the assumptions are lifted verbatim without original investigations or philosophical arguments. So every historicist worth his salt seeks multiple meanings of a text and relates it to its context without questioning why he is doing what he is doing. Given these assumptions new historicists reposition the text in the original discursive reality of the age in which it was produced.

II. INDIAN THEATRE IN ENGLISH:

Coming to the Post Independent era in Indian Theatre in English, it has brought a remarkable change in the plays written during the period. S. Krishna Bhatta in his book Indian English Drama: A Critical Study (1987) listed more than 200 hundred plays written in and around 1950. But most of them were not performed or published. But the things started changing. The writers turned directors. There

seems to be a dramatic revival, where young people are turning to theatrical study again. As written by Nirmala Ravindran India Today in its Jan. 26th 2004 issue has an article entitled “Dramatic Revival”. She talks of this generation moving away from malls and PlayStations towards theatre, seeking “the archaic thrill of the stage” which “the culture watchers are calling the second coming of theatre.” This paper is a study on such plays.

III. GURUCHARAN DAS:

Larins Saheb by Gurucharan Das is a history based text, first staged in 1969. Being Punjabi, Gurucharan Das himself says that reading the history of Punjab is searching for identity. This play is about Henry Lawrence, one of the soldiers in the British army. He tries to become Raja Ranjith Singh by manipulating Rani Jindan Kaur. Gurucharan Das very clearly emphasises the subconscious need of the British to rule us. The play runs in three acts, identifying the mindset of a widow woman, Rani Jindan Kaur to grow his son as a king and the obstructing external forces.

Dalip: What will I be like when I grow up?

Rani: You’ll be strong like a lion-just like your father.

Dalip:Yes, I’ll e the lion of victory. I’ll throw them out. (Takes out his toy sword from his belt.)

.....

Rani: (More to herself) You mustn’t see him alone⁴. (pp.17-18)

Das succeeds admirably in portraying the 19th century colonial India. After the death of Maharaja Ranjit Singh - the Lion of Punjab⁴, the British appointed Henry Lawrence as the resident of East India Company in the court of Ranjit Singh’s twelve-year-old son Dalip Singh. He is preferred over others. As Elliot a member of British Company observes that the greatest achievement of Larins Sahib is that he is able to project himself to natives as being fully sensitive to their needs. In preferring Indian officers to British in an attempt to restore Sikh self respect and to root out corruption in the Court, Lawrence alienates his superiors. However, everyone knows that he is familiar with the pulse of the natives. Hence, he is given important positions. His rise from a mere clerk to the resident of the East India Company is meteoric. He appears to be totally free from the original sin of the white man’s burden.

IV. ASIF CURRIMBHOY

Things started changing with the arrival of Asif Currimbhoy on the Indian English drama scene. He was one of our first playwrights to produce plays that could be performed. Other playwrights writing in 1960s are with more success than the earlier ones. The primary reason being that they were writing plays to be acted, the foremost of them were Nissim Ezkiel with his Nalini and Sleepwalker. Asif Currimbhoy, as said by his wife, is a “Karma Yogi”, wrote on the issues that bothered him. As so much history is used in the play, New Historicism is the best approach in analysing this play. It is said by Peter Barry, that new historicism is “a method based on the parallel reading of literary and non-literary texts, usually of the same historical period”³.

The Refugee, The title of the play gives the exact problem, the play tries to tackle. The play provokes the Bangladesh War as is given in its first scene, which begins indicating the specific time and exact place of the play and after the talks between Yahya Khan and Sheirk Mujib broke down. The play sensitively shows the treatment of refugees in general, Yassin the protagonist in particular, it depicts the traumas he gothrough and how he was misunderstood and maligned.

V. MANJULA PADMANABHAN

In her play “Lights Out” Manjula depicts the never changing attitude of our society. She addresses “as a society how responsive are we to others’ needs?” The play is on Santa Cruz, Mumbai, 1982. The reluctance to get involved, the reluctance to get out and do something, to take a stand is all authentically portrayed in this play. At one occasion she opines her play to be studied through Marxism or any other schools of criticism than feministic view.

Mohan:It’s unnatural not to look. It’s unnatural not to get involved4. (p.120)

Everyone in the play just talks of the nightly gang rape that takes place but no one is willing to do anything. They know clearly that some injustice is going on a woman or someone is forcing for sex. The Scene opens in an Apartment in Bombay, India. For over half century now, there is no specific law for woman. The play clearly examines the society around us as is said by Marx about the ‘oppressed’ and ‘the oppressing’ and also the dominating male class who own the woman either or the other way. The way it ends focuses on the chilling fact that, “ordinary middle-class people chose to stand and watch while a woman was being brutalized in a neighbouring compound.” The parallel texts for this play would be Indian History which is associated with the women. The status of women in the society is to be understood before judging the people. Where a woman enjoys equal rights to a man there we can expect actions instead of watching. The incident in the play certainly directs us towards 1982 Mumbai.

VI. ZUBIN DRIVER:

Zubin Driver is one of our prolific playwrights, who has been fascinated by Harold Pinter and Zubin’s reputation in the theatre world also rests on terms like the-theatre-of-the-absurd-guy! Zubin, today, heads The Cell, CNBC’s in-house creative agency, whose communications strategy fits in seamlessly with the marketing strategy. After finishing his Masters in Literature and Aesthetics from Mumbai, Zubin joined the arena of advertising, where he has worked with many reputed agencies, like Ogilvy and Mather, and Lintas. In 1996, the Talk Show on Sony Entertainment Television in which he was a Team Head, won the RAPA award for the best Talk Show. He has conducted a workshop on Theatre for IIM students in Bangalore and also taught Drama at a Krishnamurthi School in Uttarkashi. He does freelance writing on Drama for various newspapers.

Worm Play was written and directed by Zubin and performed in 2000. This play was also part of the productions of Spontaneous Assembly. This play in two acts gives no unity of time, place and action. It comes into the Theatre of the Absurd tradition, where there is no formal plot or characterization, because of which the two characters seem as if they have no purpose in life and emphasize “the monotony and repetitiveness of time in human affairs.”(Styan, Modern Drama)⁶. The playwright adopts stylistic methods that lend themselves to farce, and comic form, reinforcing the concept of the absurd.

Worm Play talks of worms and how they live and play in this universe. Who or what are these worms is left to the readers inferences. New Historicism can be applied here as the worms speak:

WS: history is threatening to pass us by my lord,
the country is in a state of chaos...hordes of
creatures trample around the countryside.....(p.246)

Here we need to understand the history of politicians, gods, people, communities etc. Because ‘worms’ can be inferred in any of these issues. So, co-text based on the past is required to understand the history.

VII. MAHESH DATTANI:

Mahesh Dattani is one of the most promising playwrights and being winner of Sahitya Academi Award, there are 8 plays to his credit. Any one whoever works on Indian English Theatre the first name that would come to their mind is Mahesh Dattani. Being a writer he started a theatre group called Playpen in 1986 and also directed several plays. Mahesh conducted many workshops and directed movies also.

The play *Dance like a Man* was written and first performed in Bangalore, in September 1989. To date there have been more than 200 performances of this play all over the country and abroad, many directed by Lillette Dubey, who is one of the directors Mahesh trusts. The play was published in 2000.

Mahesh explores the pathos of human predicament in subtle way. The play oscillates between the past and the present. Aristotle's six point formula beautifully fit for this play. Amritlal Parekh, father of Jairaj, is the head of the family, where his hierarchy is seen in each and every issue of the family and all the members of the family used to obey him at any cost. He was a man of liberal ideology and didn't like his son's intension and passion for dancing. So he strongly objected his association with other dancers. As the play speaks of the past in 1940s of Amritlal and the 1980s of Jairaj, those days *bharatanatyam* happens to be the art of female and male artists were very little in number, but the pioneers of the art were male only. So here also we can approach the co-text related to the dance forms history and eminent persons related to it.

VIII. CONCLUSION:

Modern Indian English Theatre is undergoing so many changes and challenging the audience to be aware of history too. Lakshmi Chandra in her preface to the course book entitled *Indian Writing in English – for Post-Graduate Diploma in the Teaching of English Programme*, says that when she started this project she discovered that there were many dramatists writing in English although a lot of their work remains unpublished. The plays she selected can be approached through New Historicism, realism, expressionism as well as Marxism. In this paper we approached New Historicism to the selected plays.

Now worldwide there is a search for identity, self discovery, finding the roots. The importance of history is identified because of this thrive. Gurucharan Das himself says when his play first staged, "Reading the history of the Punjab was for me also a search for identity."

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://www.ijsl.stir.ac.uk/issue2/wickman.html>. Accessed on 23/02/2016
- [2] Ibid.
- [3] Barry, Peter. *Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory*. New York: Manchester UP, 1995. Print. Pp.125
- [4] Chandra, Lakshmi. Ed., *Lights On! Indian Plays in English*, CIEFL, Hyd. ISBN:81-85855-00-5 (A collection of seven plays)
- [5] (All the text book references are from the above book)
- [6] *Lapis Lazuli –An International Literary Journal / Vol.I/ Issue.I /July 2011* Accessed on
- [7] A Publication of Pinter Society of India. <http://www.pintersociety.com>. Accessed on 23/02/2016
- [8] Lakshmi Chandra: *Survey of Indian Drama in English*,
- [9] <http://www.museindia.com/viewarticle.asp?myr=2007&iissid=14&id=766> Accessed on 22/02/2016.
- [10] Other Sources:
- [11] Hayman, Ronald. *How to Read a Play*. London: Methuen, 1977.
- [12] Styan, J. L. *Drama, Stage and Audience*. London. Cup, 1975
- [13] ----. *Modern Drama in Theory and Practice Vols. 1, 2, 3*, Cambridge, CUP, 1981.